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The Coldest and Densest Overflow Branch Into the North Atlantic is Stable in Transport, but Warming

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Key Points:

- Observed Faroe Bank Channel overflow strength has been stable from 1996 to 2022, but the overflow waters warmed in the recent two decades
- Concurrent salinity increase prevented the bottom water density from decreasing significantly from the effect of warming
- After entrainment downstream, the overflow contributed water of reduced density to global overturning due to non-linear effects of warming

19 Abstract

20 The overflow of cold water through the Faroe Bank Channel (FBC) is the densest water crossing
21 the Greenland-Scotland Ridge and the densest source for the Atlantic Meridional Overturning
22 Circulation (AMOC). Here, we show that the overflow volume transport remained stable from
23 1996 to 2022, but that the bottom water warmed at an average rate of 0.1 °C per decade, mainly
24 caused by warming of deep waters upstream. The salinity of the overflow water has increased as
25 a lagged and reduced response to the salinity increase seen in the upper-layer source waters.
26 Therefore, the potential density of the bottom water over the FBC sill shows no statistically
27 significant trend. After entrainment of warmer ambient waters downstream of the FBC, the
28 nonlinear density dependence upon temperature implies, however, that the overflow contributed
29 water of reduced density to the local overturning and the deep limb of the AMOC.

30 Plain Language Summary

31 As part of the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation – often called AMOC – dense water
32 is formed north of the subsea ridge between Greenland and Scotland. On its route southward at
33 depth, the dense water has to cross this subsea ridge called the Greenland-Scotland Ridge. The
34 densest water flows through the deepest trench, which is the Faroe Bank Channel with a sill
35 depth of 840 m. Here, the strength of the flow has been monitored since 1995 together with its
36 temperature and salinity characteristics. While the strength of the flow has been stable
37 throughout the monitoring period, the dense water in the Faroe Bank Channel has warmed and
38 also become more saline. Despite the warming, the density of the water, which is determined by
39 the combination of temperature and salinity, has remained nearly unchanged. After leaving the
40 Faroe Bank Channel, the dense water intensively entrains and mixes with warmer surrounding
41 water and forms a larger volume of water, termed Iceland-Scotland Overflow Water, that feeds
42 the AMOC. The density of this large volume is sensitive to warming. The observed warming of
43 the dense water may, therefore, have implications for the AMOC and thereby on the regional as
44 well as global climate.

45 1 Introduction

46 With a sill depth of 840 m (Figure 1), the Faroe Bank Channel (FBC) is the deepest passage
47 across the Greenland-Scotland Ridge, and through this channel, there is a continuous flow of
48 cold water, termed FBC-overflow (Hermann, 1959; Borenäs & Lundberg, 1988; Hansen &
49 Østerhus, 2007). Using the traditional criterion, $\sigma_\theta > 27.8 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, to define overflow water (e.g.,
50 Dickson & Brown, 1994), Hansen and Østerhus (2007) estimated the average volume transport
51 of FBC-overflow in the 1995–2005 period to be $(1.9 \pm 0.3) \text{ Sv}$ ($1 \text{ Sv} = 10^6 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$). By this
52 criterion, the FBC-overflow transports around one third of the total overflow across the ridge
53 (Østerhus et al., 2019), making it second in strength after the Denmark Strait overflow. The
54 densest component of the FBC-overflow is colder and denser than the densest component of the
55 Denmark Strait overflow (Huang et al., 2020) and the other, weaker, overflow branches
56 (Østerhus et al., 2008; Beird et al., 2013; Johnson et al., 2017).

57 The FBC-overflow, thus, is the coldest and densest source for the deep limb of the Atlantic
58 Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC). It is, however, strongly modified by entraining
59 ambient water masses on route towards the deep Atlantic Ocean. Much of the water mass
60 transformation occurs within a short distance from the FBC exit (Mauritzen et al., 2005; Geyer et
61 al., 2006; Ullgren et al., 2016). Together with the weaker Iceland-Faroe Ridge (IFR) overflow
62 (Beird et al., 2013), the FBC-overflow leaves the Iceland Basin as Iceland-Scotland Overflow
63 Water (ISOW). ISOW is composed of the overflow water masses Norwegian Sea Overflow
64 Water (NSOW) and Modified East Iceland Water (MEIW) and the ambient water masses
65 Labrador Sea Water (LSW) and Subpolar Mode Water (SPMW). The FBC-overflow carries
66 NSOW, while the IFR-overflow carries both NSOW and MEIW. However, details of IFR-
67 overflow are still missing (Johns et al., 2021). Observations indicate that the overflow
68 component of the ISOW entrains ambient waters, roughly in a one-to-one ratio (Fogelqvist et al.,
69 2003; Johns et al., 2021).

70 A one-to-one mixing ratio implies a doubling in transport, and Johns et al. (2021) found 5.3 Sv
71 of ISOW to leave the Iceland Basin based on four years of moored observations within the
72 “Overturning in the Subpolar North Atlantic Program” (OSNAP). Earlier estimates by Dickson
73 and Brown (1994) and Sarafanov et al. (2012) emphasized that overflow with entrained ambient
74 waters is the main contributor to the lower limb of the AMOC. OSNAP results have confirmed

75 this (Lozier et al., 2019) and have enhanced the role of the ISOW (Petit et al., 2020; Johns et al.,
 76 2021). In terms of volume transport, the Iceland/Rockall basins account for almost half (48%) of
 77 the overturning east of Greenland, including the Arctic Mediterranean (i.e., north of the
 78 Greenland-Scotland Ridge, GSR) according to Koman et al. (2022). Petit et al. (2020) identified
 79 local buoyancy forcing south of the GSR as the primary mechanism. However, as emphasized by
 80 Koman et al. (2022), this does not represent the density transformations, which are much more
 81 dramatic in the Arctic Mediterranean where the overflow waters are formed.

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 84 **Figure 1.** Monitoring setup and average conditions for the FBC-overflow in the 1996–2022 period. **a)** Map of the
 85 region with bathymetry based on GEBCO. Areas shallower than 500 m are grey. “FBC” is Faroe Bank Channel. “FaB”
 86 is Faroe Bank. “FaP” is Faroe Plateau. “FSC” is Faroe-Shetland Channel. The red rectangle in the FBC shows the area
 87 covered by the expanded map in **b)**. Three CTD standard sections are indicated by differently colored lines with
 88 selected standard stations indicated by circles in the same colors. **b)** Expanded map of the FBC sill region (red
 89 rectangle in **a)**) showing bottom topography, the two ADCP deployment sites (FB and FC), and two standard CTD
 90 stations (V05 and V06) on the V-section. **c)** The V-section showing average isotherms below 200m depth is based on

91 104 CTD profiles at each station in the period 1996-2022. The 0.25 °C isoline is dashed, while the continuous lines
92 are at 1 °C intervals. **d**) Sill section showing the two ADCP sites (colored circles) with sound beams illustrated by
93 colored cones. Black lines show two contours for average velocity towards 312°, see arrow in b). **e**) Average profiles
94 of temperature (red), salinity (blue), and potential density (black) for the 400 m to 800 m interval over the central sill
95 based on 20 CTD profiles located in a small region around the ADCP sites. **f**) Average velocity profiles for the 400 m
96 to 800 m interval at the two ADCP sites based on daily averaged profiles from 7446 days at FB and 4784 days at FC.
97

98 Since November 1995, temperature, salinity, and velocity of the FBC-overflow have been
99 monitored by regular hydrographic surveys and moored instrumentation. Configuration of the
100 monitoring system has been described by Hansen and Østerhus (2007) and Hansen et al. (2016),
101 including average volume transports and seasonality.

102 Time series of FBC-overflow volume transport (Hansen et al., 2016) have shown a very stable
103 transport. By contrast, the hydrographic properties of the FBC-overflow have been changing.
104 This was indicated by Hansen et al. (2016), who found a warming of the bottom water from 2002
105 to 2014. Here, we report on the continued warming of the bottom water of the channel based on
106 updated and reprocessed data (Hansen et al., 2023). We discuss concurrent changes in salinity
107 and density of the FBC-overflow water and relate these changes to upstream sources for the
108 FBC-overflow and to the Atlantic inflow. We propose that the observed warming implies a
109 reduction in the density of the water fed into the deep limb of the AMOC.

110 2 Materials and Methods

111 Acoustic Doppler Current Profilers (ADCPs) have been deployed at two fixed sites over the FBC
112 sill, FB and FC (Figure 1b,d). The deployments at FB began in November 1995, and those at FC
113 started in July 2001. Data acquisition has been continuous except for annual servicing periods,
114 typically lasting around 20 days, and occasional gaps due to mooring or instrument failure. The
115 velocity profiles from the ADCPs have been quality controlled (see Hansen et al., 2016 for
116 details). Since the deep part of the FBC is very narrow at the sill (Figure 1d), a value for the
117 “kinematic volume transport” (i.e., based on velocity data) may be estimated from the ADCP
118 profile at site FB alone (Hansen & Østerhus, 2007; Hansen et al., 2016).

119 Temperature at the ADCPs has been monitored, partly by the temperature sensor of the ADCP
120 and partly by high-quality temperature loggers (SeaBird SBE37 or SBE39), which have been

121 attached to the ADCP since 2001 at site FB and since 2015 at site FC. With the ADCPs at most 8
122 m above the bottom at both sites, the temperature at the instrument may be considered the
123 bottom temperature within an accuracy of 0.001 °C. The bottom temperature time series at sites
124 FB and FC have been quality controlled and calibrated, as documented in a technical report
125 (Hansen et al., 2023). The temperature observations from the high-quality temperature loggers
126 have uncertainties of at most 0.01 °C, but the ADCP temperature observations are more
127 uncertain (Hansen et al., 2016). Comparison with adjacent conductivity-temperature-depth
128 (CTD) profiles and attached high-quality temperature loggers have enabled re-calibrations that
129 reduce the uncertainty of the ADCP temperature sensor to 0.02 °C for annual averages (Hansen
130 et al., 2023).

131 To facilitate annual average temperature estimates, two different methods have been employed to
132 correct for the effect of the annual servicing periods and other occasional gaps on the bottom
133 temperature at site FB (Hansen et al., 2023). The “Common period” temperature at FB, $T_{\text{FB,Cp}}$, is
134 the average of all daily values except for the period from day number 136 (mid-May) to day
135 number 195 (mid-July) including most data gaps. The alternative, “Gap-filled”, bottom
136 temperature at FB, $T_{\text{FB,Gf}}$, is corrected for gaps using an average “seasonal anomaly” (Hansen et
137 al., 2023). At FC, bottom temperature is only calculated for the common period and is denoted
138 T_{FC} .

139 To estimate hydrographic properties upstream of the FBC sill, we use SeaBird SBE911+ CTD
140 data from regular (typically four times a year) occupations of 11 standard stations around the
141 Faroes (Figure 1). These stations include two (V05 and V06) located just southeast of the sill,
142 three stations on the S-section in the Faroe-Shetland Channel (FSC), and six stations on the N-
143 section on the western boundary of the Norwegian Sea. The data have been quality controlled,
144 and salinity calibrated against water samples. Their typical accuracy for overflow water is
145 estimated at 0.001 °C and 0.002 g kg⁻¹ for salinity. Salinities are reported following TEOS-10
146 Absolute Salinity scale with δS_A set to zero (<https://www.teos-10.org/>), while temperatures are
147 reported as Conservative Temperatures or in situ, when not specified.

148 3 Results

149 Average conditions are summarized in Figure 1 based on data updated to 2022. The bottom parts
150 of the channel are dominated by the cold low-salinity overflow water (Figure 1c,e). The above-
151 lying warmer and more saline water is a shallow and warm component of SPMW, which is
152 traditionally termed “Atlantic inflow” (e.g., Hansen et al., 2016), since it is part of the Atlantic
153 inflow to the Arctic Mediterranean, which is the main source water for the overflow (Hansen &
154 Østerhus, 2000; Østerhus et al., 2019). The vertical velocity structure (Figure 1d,f) shows a
155 relatively weak flow in the upper layers increasing to strong uni-directional flow in the overflow
156 layer with average velocities exceeding 1 m s^{-1} in the core. Temporal variations of key
157 parameters characterizing the FBC-overflow and upstream waters are illustrated in Figure 2.

158 3.1 Overflow volume transport

159 Annual values for the kinematic volume transport of the overflow water extend the time series
160 presented in Hansen et al. (2016) by additional eight years, maintaining the overall conclusion of
161 stability with a long term mean of $(2.2 \pm 0.2) \text{ Sv}$. Over the whole period, the annual averages
162 exhibit a slight positive trend, but it is not significantly different from zero (Figure 2).

163 3.2 The temperature of the bottom water over the FBC sill

164 The two different estimates for the annual bottom temperature at FB are shown in Figure 2. They
165 are almost identical and the difference is within the uncertainty estimate of $0.01 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, except for
166 2009 and 2022 where it is slightly higher. This implies that the annual average is not sensitive to
167 the method used to account for the data gaps. The anomalously high temperature in 2012 raises
168 suspicion. However, temperature data from FC, available only until late May, confirm the
169 occurrence of concurrent warm pulses during spring 2012, which largely explain the anomaly.

170 Comparing data from seven years with high-accuracy temperature loggers at both sites, Hansen
171 et al. (2023) found the average difference between bottom temperature at FB and FC to be $+0.07$
172 $^\circ\text{C}$ ($T_{\text{FB}} - T_{\text{FC}}$). Based on CTD data, most of this difference is not due to difference in bottom
173 depth (30 m), but rather that the temperature at these depths decreases towards the Faroe Bank
174 (Figure 1c, Hansen et al., 2023). On annual time scales, the bottom temperature at FB minus 0.07

175 °C should therefore be a good estimator of the coldest overflow water crossing the Greenland-
 176 Scotland Ridge.

177 The time series of bottom temperature at FC has several gaps. The bottom water at FC is colder
 178 than at FB, but the temporal variation is similar at both sites. This confirms that the bottom water
 179 of the FBC has warmed throughout the monitoring period. From Figure 2, the warming started
 180 around 2004 and has continued since, although irregularly and with occasional reversing trends.
 181 For the six years with acceptable data before this start (1996–2003), the average value of $T_{FB,Gf}$
 182 was -0.46 °C. From this baseline, the bottom temperature increased to $T_{FB,Gf} = -0.21$ °C for the
 183 last three years in our data set (2020–2022). The linear trend for the 2000 – 2022 period was
 184 (0.11 ± 0.02) °C per decade with a 95% confidence interval.

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 187 **Figure 2.** Temporal variations of FBC-overflow and upstream waters 1996–2022. The black curve at the top shows annually
 188 averaged kinematic volume transport of the FBC-overflow using the right-hand scale. All the other curves show annually averaged
 189 temperature using the left-hand scale. The bottom temperature at site FB is shown in cyan ($T_{FB,Cp}$), and red ($T_{FB,Gf}$), where error
 190 bars indicate the instrumental uncertainty of $T_{FB,Gf}$. The bottom temperature at site FC, T_{FC} , is shown in brown. Data gaps are
 191 indicated by dashed lines. The orange curve shows the average Conservative Temperature at the $\sigma_{\theta} = 28.05$ kg m^{-3} isopycnal for
 192 water between N05 and N10 on the N-section. Semi-transparent areas with the same colors as the curves for volume transport
 193 (black), $T_{FB,Cp}$ (cyan), and N-section Conservative Temperature (orange) show average \pm standard error where the standard errors
 194 for the two regular time series (volume transport and $T_{FB,Cp}$) have been corrected for serial correlation (von Storch, 1999).

195

196 Most of the FBC-overflow is produced (leaves the surface) outside the Norwegian Sea (Huang et
197 al., 2020; Brakstad et al., 2023), but it must pass through the Norwegian Sea, preferably over its
198 western rim (Yang & Pratt, 2013; Semper et al., 2020) where it passes through the N-section
199 (Figure 1). After crossing the section, it sometimes exhibits an eastward excursion before re-
200 circulating back towards the Faroe-Shetland Channel (Chafik et al., 2020). According to Hátún et
201 al., (2021), most of the overflow water passes between stations N05 and N10 (Figure 1a) and the
202 orange curve in Figure 2 shows the Conservative Temperature for water between these two
203 stations on the $\sigma_{\theta} = 28.05 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ isopycnal, which is similar to the potential density close to the
204 bottom of the FBC (Figure 1e). The linear trend of this series was $(0.12 \pm 0.02) \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C per decade}$
205 with a 95% confidence interval, which is similar to the trend for $T_{\text{FB,Gf}}$. This result is not
206 sensitive to the choice of stations on the N-section (Figure S1). We can therefore conclude that
207 most of the warming at the bottom of the FBC sill since 2004 can be ascribed to warming of the
208 upstream waters in the Norwegian Sea.

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212 **Figure 3.** Temporal variations of temperature, salinity, and potential density at the locations indicated in Figure 1a. Results from
 213 standard sections have the same colors as the sections in Figure 1a. Semi-transparent areas around selected (to prevent visual
 214 overlap) curves show average \pm one standard error. **a)** In situ temperature at fixed depths on the N-section (orange) and on the S-
 215 section (blue). **b)** Conservative Temperature on four isopycnal surfaces at the N-section (orange) and the S-section (blue). **c)**
 216 Annually averaged salinity at V06 and on the S-section and N-section at the depths where the Conservative Temperatures are equal
 217 to the Conservative Temperature at the bottom of FB, θ_{FB} , for the same year. The box in the lower right-hand corner shows linear
 218 trends with 95% confidence limits for the whole period in units of $10^{-3} \text{ g kg}^{-1}$. **d)** Annually averaged salinity of Atlantic inflow
 219 cores, defined as a 50 m deep layer with maximum average salinity along a section (V: magenta; N: orange) or shelf edge station
 220 (S: blue) (Larsen et al., 2012). **e)** Annually averaged potential density, σ_θ , on V06 and on the N-section, and the S-section at the
 221 depths where the Conservative Temperatures are equal to θ_{FB} for the same year. The box in the upper right-hand corner shows
 222 linear trends with 95% confidence limits for the whole period in units of $10^{-4} \text{ kg m}^{-3}$. **f)** Annually averaged potential density, σ_θ , of
 223 idealized ISOW generated as an equal mixture between bottom water from the FBC and either LSW or SPMW. The properties of
 224 LSW and SPMW were kept fixed, while the properties of the FBC bottom water each year had the Conservative Temperature θ_{FB}
 225 and Absolute Salinity at θ_{FB} on V06. The dashed lines are regression lines and the trends are listed with 95% confidence limits.

226

227 3.3 Vertical extent of the overflow water warming

228 The amount of CTD data over the FBC sill is not sufficient to estimate how far up into the
229 overflow layer the observed bottom water warming extends. The data coverage is better at
230 standard stations V05 and V06, a short distance upstream (Figure 1b), but there are still only a
231 few CTD profiles a year and the temperature field is highly dynamic with strong short-term
232 variations (Figure S2) that decrease the statistical significance of estimated trends. Instead,
233 Figure 3a shows annually averaged temperatures at two other standard sections that should
234 represent overflow water upstream of the sill. All the curves in Figure 3a indicate warming with
235 similar trends that may collectively be expressed as (0.10 ± 0.03) °C per decade with 95%
236 confidence limits. Upstream, waters at the same depths as the overflow layer over the FBC sill,
237 thus, have warmed at the same rate as the FBC bottom water. However, ocean water tends to
238 flow along constant potential density rather than constant depth. A more appropriate picture is
239 presented in Figure 3b, which shows variations of the Conservative Temperature upstream on
240 four isopycnals that cover most of the FBC-overflow layer (Figure 1e). Over the whole 1996 –
241 2022 period, all of the curves in Figure 3b exhibited statistically significant warming. For the σ_{θ}
242 = 28.05 kg m⁻³ isopycnal on the N-section, the trend was (0.12 ± 0.02) °C per decade. However,
243 after 2015, the warming appears to have stagnated at the denser levels and reversed for the
244 lightest components.

245 3.4 Salinity variations

246 Conductivity and pressure sensors associated with some of the high-accuracy temperature
247 loggers (SBE37) allow salinity to be calculated, but the results are too unstable to provide a time
248 series of overflow salinity. Instead, we use CTD data from standard stations upstream of the FBC
249 sill. Given that salinity at fixed depth is highly variable with time, overflow salinity for each year
250 at one of these stations is estimated as the average salinity at the same Conservative Temperature
251 as the bottom water at ADCP site FB that year. With typical temperature and salinity values, the
252 Conservative Temperature on the bottom at FB, Θ_{FB} , is equal to the in situ temperature minus
253 0.032 °C, and we define $\Theta_{FB} = T_{FB,Gf} - 0.032$ °C. To estimate the bottom salinity at FBC each
254 year, we therefore use the salinity at this Conservative Temperature upstream for that particular
255 year.

256 The resulting time series of salinity at Conservative Temperature Θ_{FB} upstream of the FBC sill
257 are shown in Figure 3c. Generally, the salinity increases as the overflow water proceeds from the
258 S-section (blue) to station V06 (red) located approximately 20 km southeast of the sill. This
259 increase may partly be explained by diapycnal mixing along the way from the S-section to the
260 FBC sill area, which will tend to erode the salinity minimum around 0 °C on the Θ -S curve
261 (Figure S3, updated from Hansen et al., 2016). Alternatively, the salinity increase from the S-
262 section to the V-section may be caused by entrainment of the more saline above-lying Atlantic
263 inflow to the Arctic Mediterranean. Figure 3d shows three different time series of Atlantic inflow
264 salinity. Their average values are different (Larsen et al., 2012), but they all have similar
265 temporal variations with decreasing Atlantic inflow salinities after 2010 and especially after
266 2015 (Holliday et al., 2020).

267 Local entrainment of Atlantic inflow water into the overflow layer, therefore, cannot explain the
268 temporal salinity increases in Figure 3c. Instead, this increase appears to be caused by salinity
269 increases at the upstream sources. The overflow water is formed in the Arctic Mediterranean
270 mainly from Atlantic inflow (Østerhus et al., 2019) by various regionally and temporally varying
271 processes (e.g., Eldevik et al., 2009; Almeida et al., 2023). A lagged regression analysis indicates
272 that variations of the overflow water properties may be seen as a lagged (by 8–18 years) and
273 reduced (by a factor around 5 or more) response to changes in Atlantic inflow properties (Figure
274 S4).

275 The motivation for using upstream salinity at the same Conservative Temperature as at the FBC
276 sill the same year was based on the assumption of isopycnal flow. If this assumption holds, and
277 salinity is conserved along the flow, then the choice of equal Conservative Temperatures implies
278 equal potential density at the FBC sill and upstream. However, Figure 3c clearly shows that
279 salinity is not conserved along the flow, particularly from the S-section to the V-section. Despite
280 this, the three salinity curves in this figure have similar temporal trends. Additionally, station
281 V06 is only 20 km upstream of the sill. Therefore, we argue that the temporal salinity increases
282 upstream, especially at V06, imply a similar salinity increase at the FBC sill.

283 3.5 Implications for the local overturning and the AMOC

284 Based on this argument, the salinities from Figure 3c have been combined with the Conservative
285 Temperature at site FB to calculate potential density each year (Figure 3e). Over the entire period

286 1996–2022, potential densities at the N-section and the S-section did not exhibit statistically
287 significant trends. However, station V06 had a marginally significant negative trend, which was
288 caused by a potential density decrease after 2015 (Figure 3e). During this period, the bottom
289 temperature at ADCP site FB continued to rise (Figure 2) even though the Conservative
290 Temperature remained almost constant at the two deepest isopycnals in Figure 3b. This might
291 indicate that the bottom water over the FBC sill after 2015 has been drawn from slightly less
292 dense, and therefore warmer, upstream waters due to deepening upstream isopycnals (Figure S5),
293 conceivably caused by a lagged response to reduced Atlantic inflow salinity after 2010 (Figure
294 3d).

295 The evidence, however, is weak and we cannot claim that the density of the FBC-overflow
296 decreased in the 1996 – 2022 period, which would directly impact the AMOC. Instead, the
297 warming will have indirect impacts on the overturning in the Northeast Atlantic or the AMOC.
298 As discussed in Sect. 1, the overflow water mixes roughly in a one-to-one ratio with ambient
299 waters before leaving the Iceland Basin as ISOW. The ambient waters are mainly LSW and
300 SPMW (Fogelqvist et al., 2003; Johns et al., 2021). The relative effect of temperature and
301 salinity variations on density are different at high and low temperatures, which implies that when
302 the overflow by entraining warmer water is raised to a higher temperature, its potential density
303 becomes more sensitive to overflow temperature variations.

304 The effect of this is exemplified in Figure 3f, where we consider an idealized case with FBC
305 bottom water mixing with equal amounts of either LSW or SPMW. The properties of LSW and
306 SPMW are kept constant in time, equal to the values cited by Johns et al. (2021) (LSW: $\theta = 3.85$
307 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, $S_p = 34.92$ and SPMW: $\theta = 7$ $^{\circ}\text{C}$, $S_p = 35.2$) converted to Conservative Temperature and
308 Absolute Salinity, whereas the properties of FBC bottom water vary every year according to the
309 observations. While there is no significant trend in density for the undiluted overflow water
310 within the FBC, the trend becomes highly significant after the overflow water has been raised to
311 a higher temperature by entrainment. The recent large freshening seen in Atlantic inflow after
312 2015 (Holliday et al., 2020; Figure 3d) is likely yet to fully emerge in FBC salinity. Considering
313 the estimated delay of 8-18 years, a freshening scenario may unfold in the very near future along
314 with ongoing warming.

315 4 Conclusions

316 Annually averaged volume transport of FBC-overflow has remained relatively stable throughout
317 the observational period from 1996 to 2022 (Figure 2). By contrast, the bottom temperature over
318 the FBC sill has increased. The warming seems to have started around 2004. Over the
319 observational period, the bottom temperature increased by around 0.25 °C, equivalent to an
320 average warming rate of 0.1 °C per decade.

321 The warming over the bottom of the FBC is similar to and mainly caused by warming of the
322 upstream waters at similar depths and isopycnals in the Norwegian Sea. CTD observations
323 upstream also indicate that the warming extends far up into the overflow layer (Figure 3a and
324 Figure 3b).

325 Concurrent with the warming, the salinity of the FBC bottom water has also increased (Figure
326 3c) as a lagged and reduced response to the salinity variation of the Atlantic inflow (Figure 3d).
327 This can also explain why the FBC bottom water salinity has remained relatively constant after
328 2015.

329 Due to the concurrent salinity increase, the warming has only caused a marginally significant
330 trend of the potential density of the FBC bottom water, although there are indications of a
331 decrease in the most recent years (Figure 3e). Despite this, the FBC-overflow, after entrainment
332 of ambient water, likely contributed water of reduced density to the overturning in the Iceland
333 Basin and the AMOC. This is because of the warming of the overflow water and the effect of the
334 non-linear dependence of density on temperature (Figure 3f).

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435 Open Research

436 Time series of FBC overflow transport, FBC bottom temperature and Atlantic water properties
437 are available as text files at <http://envofar.fo/data/index.php?dir=Timeseries&sort=N&order=A>.
438 FBC current data and hydrographic data are available as text files at
439 <http://www.envofar.fo/index.php?page=climate>.